

Disaster Logistics: The disaster supply chain and the role of human behavior

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Abstract

All over the world, populations are confronted with natural and man-made disasters. Every emergency can be resolved by applying logical reasoning. During a disaster, the crisis managers are faced with many unknown circumstances because they don't know what happened, who is affected, how extensive the damage is, etc. A successful response to a disaster is characterized by the success of the objective to reduce the vulnerability of the people affected in the shortest amount of time with the least amount of available resources. In this context, agile, adaptable and capable supply chains are needed. During disasters, human behaviour in the form of immediate action is essential. The behaviour of crisis management personnel plays a crucial role in disaster response. Research suggests simple plans and realistic preparations with the possibility for improvisations and with an emphasis on public awareness. Those responding to disasters (e.g. rescue teams) must be able to align the various needs and dynamic roles of many players. In this context, the following research questions arise: 1) Which factors influence the disaster supply chain and 2) how can we optimize the performance between rescue teams to be better prepared for disasters? The authors use a multi-method approach (including expert interviews, document analysis, and observations) by referencing a large scale exercise with the objective of identifying the supporting and hindering factors on disaster supply chains.

Keywords: Disasters, rescue teams, supply chain, human behaviour

1. Introduction

In 2010, a total of 950 disasters were registered worldwide, the second highest level ever recorded in history. The year 2010 contained more natural disasters and accidents of varying types as have occurred before, including “great natural catastrophes” such as the earthquakes in Haiti, Chile and China, the flood in Pakistan as well as the forest and moor fires in Russia. Also, in Europe, an increasing number of disasters over the past decade must be considered, as well.

Figure 1 presents examples of major incidents in Europe, traumatic events that have affected people. Major incidents normally overwhelm the regularly available rescue resources in terms of rescue personnel, transport vehicles and hospital capacity (Adler et al. 2011). The terms disaster, major incident, mass casualty incident and emergency may be considered as one and the same. A major incident is any type of emergency event or situation which can arise from natural hazards (such as snow, floods etc.), human-made disasters (such as rail accidents, motorway pileups, terrorism etc.), or industrial accidents (such as oil spills, factory fires etc.), which threaten or cause serious damage to human welfare, the environment and security.

Figure 1: Selected major incidents in Europe (Adler and Eller 2013).

The impact of disasters can be enormous. For example, in Europe between 1980 to September 2008 natural disasters caused a number of victims and economic effects, which are listed in Table 1.

No of events:	1,190
No of people killed:	121,644
Average killed per year:	4,195
No of people affected:	33,031,632
Average affected per year:	1,139,022
Economic Damage (US\$ X 1,000):	266,918,923
Economic Damage per year (US\$ X 1,000):	9,204,101

Table 1: Overview of disasters in Europe from 1980 to September 2008 (PreventionWeb 2014).

Independent of the destructive power of disasters, the question of how optimal response management should look like arises. For researchers and decision makers, the challenge is how to develop plans and manage rescue teams in order to get people out of a disaster and to get aid into the impacted areas (Richey 2009).

In the following, the authors present the results of a qualitative study from a disaster control exercise. Here, research questions arise: 1) *Which factors influence the disaster supply chain?* and 2) *how we can optimize the performance to be better prepared for disasters?*

In the context of a disaster, the behaviour of crisis management personnel plays a crucial role in the disaster response efforts and self-organization of people (Kovács and Spens 2007). Ten Brinke et al. (2010) call for simple plans and realistic preparations with the possibility for improvisations, with an emphasis on public awareness. Those responding to disasters (e.g. rescue teams) must be able to align the various needs and dynamic roles of many players (van Wassenhove 2006).

Crisis management implies operating under conditions of extreme stress caused by, for instance, multiple tasking, rapid decision-making or working under risk and high time pressure. The availability of adequate cognitive and behavioural strategies to deal with stress (i.e. “coping strategies”) is decisive in working efficiently and limiting the risk of stress-related physical and mental diseases (Lazarus and Folkman 1984; Vila and Guerra Muñoz 2009). Within a rescue operation, rescue and emergency workers have to face different stressors which can be unpredictable, un-explainable, and uncontrollable. Memory and decision-making under stress can be affected. Complex situations on the scene and different statuses of situation awareness complicate communication processes (Adler and Haus 2013). The authors use a case study with a multi-method approach (including expert interviews, document analysis, and observations). The paper starts with the description of the case study, followed by the presentation of the methodology. In the next step, the authors present selected results of the qualitative study. In the discussion portion, the results are related to existing theory. The paper finishes with the conclusion.

4. Empirical Research

4.1 *The Methodology*

The scope of this research is of a qualitative nature. The starting point of qualitative social research is a social phenomenon. For this study, a disaster control exercise, with a serious fire in a castle that affected many persons was investigated. Case study research may be chosen in order to understand complex social phenomena (Yin 2003). Disasters are characterized as complex phenomena. Qualitative research enables researchers to study the context, complexity, and ambiguity of a phenomenon (Cassell et al. 2006). It provides a systemic view of a situation or problem with an unlimited number of variables and their links (Gummesson 2007). Consequently, qualitative research frequently encompasses multiple methods in order to extract narratives of people’s views of reality and to create text from words and discourses (Gephart 2004).

This research project is based on multiple data sets. The data were collected by semi-structured individual interviews, observations and discussions. *First*, the objectives of the interviews were to collect subjective experiences and attitudes of crisis managers of the participating organizations such as the Fire Brigade, Police, Political Representatives, Emergency Call Centre, Red Cross, and Emergency Pastoral Care. In total, eight crisis managers were interviewed. Each interview was recorded, taped, transcribed to paper and analyzed by the qualitative method GABEK (GANzheitliche BÈwältigung von Komplexität). *Second*, the event was observed by eight researchers. At the beginning of the exercise, they were instructed of the observations objectives. The researchers were positioned by each participating organization. In certain cases, they were able to accompany the crisis managers. The results of the observations were summarized in reports. *Third*, group discussions about positive and negative experiences and wishes of the participating persons (crisis managers, staff, volunteers and victims) were collected on 13 posters. They were also analysed with the qualitative method GABEK.

3.1 *The Case*

On the 15th of November, 2013, a large scale exercise in the castle Puchberg, situated in Upper Austria, was organized. The castle serves as a training centre for different stakeholder groups and offers accommodations for the clients. During a symposium in the later afternoon, a major fire emerged that caused several deaths and injuries in the accommodations of the castle.

In addition to official representatives of the municipality, employees of the castle Puchberg, volunteers from the Fire Brigade, representatives of the Federal State Upper Austria and Municipality (Emergency Call Centre, Emergency Task Force), the local Red Cross (provision and transport to the hospital as well as the management of the psycho-social emergency help and information centre) and Police, as well as a team from the Emergency Pastoral Care participated in the large scale exercise.

By simulating a large scale exercise, the crisis management responsible tested different things like the alarming system, the existing rescue and evacuation plans, the personnel, the equipment, the technical solutions (e.g. crisis management system—diary), the interconnectedness, the psycho-social emergency help and information centre of the Red Cross. A detailed scenario description in the form of a screenplay was developed beforehand. The involved organizations, rescue teams and crisis managers were confronted with several challenges. The participants of the symposium had to be evacuated. The rescue teams took care of the injured people and provided them with medical and psychological support. At the same time, the disaster was activated by the Emergency Call Centre through the federal warning head office. Further objectives of the exercise were the evacuation and identification of heavily burned bodies, the improvement of the collaboration of the participating organizations as well as the training of the operational procedures in the case of an emergency between the Fire Brigade, Red Cross, Police, Emergency Pastoral Care and responsible authorities.

Figure 2: Impressions of the disaster control exercise (available photos for the press release).

3.2 The Data Analysis

The observations were summarized by the researchers based on defined guidelines. The software GABEK-WinRelan was used for the analysis of the text (interviews and posters). GABEK-WinRelan supports the analysis of large, unstructured quantities of text based on everyday language and offers different steps to identify the most relevant concepts. Notes, texts, quotations, or knowledge areas that are compressed into transparent meaning nets serve as a basis for the analysis. The diversity of analysis steps allows for identifying relations, evaluating options, setting objectives, and recognizing trends (Buber and Kraler 2000; Zelger

and Oberprantacher 2002; Zelger 2008; Zelger et al. 2011). The coding process is at the heart of the GABEK analysis. In the study, the first coding focuses on the identification of keywords which represent the semantic content of a text unit (i.e., the qualitative dimension of keyword coding). With the help of the keywords, linguistic nets and cause/effect relations can be developed. Linguistic nets can be used to visualize how the concepts relate to each other. In the following, the authors present summaries of the observation reports that are confirmed by figures from the GABEK analysis.

4. Findings

From the observation and interviews with crisis managers of the different rescue teams (Local Authorities Crisis Management Team, Fire Brigade, Emergency Call Centre, Emergency Task Force, Red Cross, Emergency Pastoral Care) as well as from the results of the discussion groups, several topics have been identified that influenced positively and negatively the disaster relief supply chain during the rescue. In the following, those aspects that were commonly observed at all places and participating organizations of the exercise are presented, namely:

- Local conditions and space
- Crisis managers
- Teams
- Information and communication
- Resources available

Local conditions and space. The local conditions and space play a central role in the way processes are run and decisions are made during an emergency. The better the local conditions for the rescue teams, the better the members may contribute to the emergency process of the people affected. *First*, the perimeter of the castle was spacious, with many different exits. The rescue teams had problems keep the people affected together. *Second*, the people affected had problems with orientation—where to go because of missing signs (e.g. signs to the psycho-social emergency help and information centre). *Third*, the rescue teams and rescued people had difficulties knowing where to go because of the old, branched building. The more that people became involved and gave and received clear instructions (e.g. in the form of warnings and information signs), the better the orientation and escape was (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Orientation problems (data from discussions/posters).

The Local Authority’s Crisis management Team was placed in a narrow room in the old castle without the possibility of airing it. Most of the members of the group did not sit down at the big table (only two persons sat down). The others moved around the room all of the time. The briefings also happened in standing positions. Because of the limited space of the room, the heat and the bad air, and the growing hectic pace due to ongoing movements, symptoms of fatigue arose. In contrast, the Emergency Call Centre was centred in the building of a municipal energy supplier in the capital city. Compared to the Emergency Task Force, it disposes of an ample office with work stations for a huge number of agents. The leading group of the team was centred in the middle of the office. During the exercise, external representatives from other rescue teams arrived to organize the information flow between their organizations located outside and the Emergency Call Centre. For all of them, work stations were available. The space allows more individual liberty for retreats, for necessary phone calls or strategic thinking with regard to the next steps. At each work station, the situated team members focused on their tasks and interacted in the case of open questions or unclear situations. In this case, they met in the front of the work stations of the leading group. All of the time, a silent working atmosphere was observed.

Crisis manager. Crisis managers are golden and silver commanders of institutions like Red Cross, Fire Brigades, and Public Authorities (non-police organizations) which are involved in the crisis management of a mass casualty incident. In their positions, these people belonging to the middle and higher management have staff and decision-making responsibilities. In our case, the crisis manager had an enormous influence on how disaster relief supply chains work. Some of the crisis managers are characterized by concentration, authority, poise, and the ability to remain calm. In addition to the focus on the event, they always kept an eye on their staff as well as complimented and acknowledged them despite the hectic rush. At the same time, they gave a feeling of security in difficult situations and disposed of competences in decision-making. They are the important links to other emergency response organisations. The central communication between the emergency response organisations is managed by the crisis managers (see Figure 4). It was observed that in some cases, crisis managers were overextended with the situation, especially in the case of people who are not integrated regularly in rescue operations. The missing experiences as well as trainings have caused a high level of stress. Additionally, newly formed groups (e.g. Local Authorities Crisis Management Team) generate a feeling of insecurity due to the absence of knowledge of the team members.

Figure 4: The role of crisis managers (data from interviews with crisis managers).

Teams. The cooperation in the teams has a positive impact on the relief processes. Those teams who were adjusted in their activities and responsibilities were able to deliver good results. They are characterized by clear structures and defined roles. The better they know each other, the higher the trust and appreciation. In the case of the local authority's crisis management team, the team was regrouped into smaller units with different crisis managers who did not know each other. The newly-formed team had difficulties in cooperation and priority setting in the decision-making processes. Compared to other teams, the local authority's crisis management team is composed of different representatives of various rescue organisations (e.g. Red Cross, Fire Brigade, etc.) from different parts of the county (Upper Austria) who do not normally work together. The cooperation was characterized by inconsistencies, for example, in the way of coordination and decision-making processes or responsibilities as well as competences.

Figure 5: The collaboration in teams (data from interviews with crisis managers).

Information. One of the most important success factors in handling a critical incident is the information management. Information ambiguity causes stress and insecurity. Technology is seen as supporting (e.g. fast communication exchange between organisations) but also as a hindrance when problems arise (e.g. when mobile phones or radios do not work). Rescue teams also criticised missing signs in the Castle which served as a base for locating and evacuating victims. The quality of information is represented by, for example, the correct admission of all people injured, dead persons and other people affected; by the way interpretations of situations are undertaken; and by the evaluation of the information with regard to its priority as well as by the liaison men who act as wheels for information exchange. Additionally, the importance of the transfer of information to team members and between crisis managers is highlighted by the interviewed crisis managers. In this context, the establishment of a communication structure with defined responsibilities (e.g. communication with the media) is of importance for a successful handling of the situation. In the case of missing staff at certain locations (e.g. at the Call Centre, no liaison officer for the Fire Brigade and Red Cross was positioned), the information deficits are represented in the handling of the processes. Also, the transfer of relevant information did not work well at some places. For example, the transfer of the list of the registered people from the Red Cross to the Local Authority's Crisis Management Team, or Call Centre, took too long. In the following, the relatives calling the Call Centre were not able to supply earlier with updated information. The check of missing persons by the police was also late-onset. Missing responsibilities and related tasks have been identified as reasons for not transferring the information to relevant organizations.

Figure 6: Information (data from interviews with crisis managers).

Resources available. Finally, the availability or absence of different resources (e.g. materials, information, human resources) affect positively or negatively the rescue and support process. The absence of resources caused the need for improvisations that were related to difficulties in rescuing people or in providing them with medical or psychosocial support. For example, Figure 7 refers to the problem that many people affected worried about too many rescue persons being in charge. They asked for more continuity in the provision of care. Additionally, some cases were observed where people who were injured or affected were given the cold shoulder by rescue teams for a long period of time.

Figure 7: Resources in the care of people affected (data from discussions/posters).

At certain stages, too many staff members were perceived negatively by the persons affected. Rescue members could not be located because of wrong information. On the other hand, having too few human resources available caused waiting times because of unexpected events (e.g. more people that must be evacuated caused waiting times at several places). Also, unexpected situations have posed challenges for the rescue teams (e.g. foreign languages) and asked for improvisations.

2. Discussion

During and after crisis situations, public and private organizations have to manage human, informational, technological, physical and financial resources. *“Supply chains dealing with disaster and crisis situations will need to correctly manage valuable, rare, inimitable, and organizationally specific resources to accomplish goals.”* (Richey 2009:622). For example, in the area of psychosocial services, the choice of an alternative supply chain rests to a great degree on two factors: if these services are provided by the public or private sector and its physical distribution. However, most critical, unlike material supplies, is the availability of manpower to provide these services. Recent research has shown that in a disaster, a majority of health care workers will not likely report to their posts and while not empirically demonstrated as of yet, this will probably be the case for a large number of psychosocial services. These organisations are working mostly on a voluntary and honorary basis - so they can't be forced to show up at the disaster scene. Another is the hierarchy of the organization itself and the ability of administrators to be flexible and adapt to changing requirements where resilience has been found to be associated with field employee's ability to adapt in contrast to managerial level personnel who are tied to administrative regulations.

Supply chains, however, depend on the ability of each link in the chain to remain viable during a disaster. This has proven to be extremely difficult without putting into place a set of contingency plans when it is likely that one or more supply or recipient organizations will fail to provide either services or materials. As a result, contingency plans must rest on an assessment of the resilience and viability of alternative supply organizations. Those organizations likely to be disrupted or whose supply line/distribution network is likely to be at

risk should be focused on either seeking alternative supply routes or means of strengthening resilience.

The question of how the planning and preparedness should be organized to manage disasters arises. Heath (1995) argues that planning and preparedness must go hand-in-hand. *“Without efficient and effective planning, preparedness soon becomes non-preparedness, with time lost in deciding what to do and potentially much wastage of resources”* (Heath 1995:23).

The observed large scale exercise in Puchberg has shown that the rescue operations within different stages run for different populations at the same time. Some of them are relevant for more than one stage, for example, the psychosocial support. The psycho-social support is seen very often in the end of the disaster supply chain. However, this service has to start being planned immediately after the rescue of the people affected. Situation awareness and correct and quick distribution of relevant information are needed for psycho-social support, as well as for crisis management purposes like tactical and strategic planning.

Maon et al. (2009) criticise that some organizations and agencies focus too much on the emergency operations and tactical planning. The different scopes may hinder an efficient way of disaster reactions if, for example, other organizations focus on longer-term operations, such as rehabilitation. It also depends on the form of the disaster where sometimes the different organizations with their actions must go hand in hand or deliver prior work that is needed as kind of an established basis for further actions of other institutions. Here again, the holistic perspective of disasters and supply chain disasters is expressed.

However, planning must be accompanied by strategic preparedness. Heath (1995) highlights the importance of integration, communication, and strategic planning. The less these components are integrated, the more likely it will be that problems, such as slow interactions between the organizations or a hindered information flow, occur. As a result, behaviour that is not controlled, a vacuum in the decision-finding and acting but also emotional reactions may emerge. Plans have to work as guides for actions by the involved teams.

The rescue of people during and after a disaster requests a number of partners. In this context, Richey (2009) also refers to the components collaboration and communication relevance for the management of disasters. In this context, it is important to find strategies that help the partners collaborate effectively and improve their relationships. For example, long-term commitment could be one answer for this collaboration.

Finally, Maon et al. (2009) ask for a concrete presentation of the current practices and characteristics of disaster relief supply chains. The better the challenges and barriers are identified, the more we are in the position to create efficient supply chain management practices. In this context, four issues—strategizing, learning, coordinating and measuring—should be taken into consideration. A supply chain model must take the alliances and collaborations between the disaster relief organizations into consideration, including their capabilities and scopes.

5. Conclusions

Although we only discussed one large scale exercise, the analysis of the data shows the main topics: local conditions and space, crisis managers, teams, information and communication, and available resources. As we know that catastrophic events will not follow a well-known algorithm, it is necessary to be aware that the most effective crisis management is characterized by the ability to adapt and adjust. Human behaviour can be unpredictable under stressful situations. People’s responses to mass casualty incidents may follow psychological patterns such as denial, anxiousness, and downgrading risk importance. Well planned, adjustable and flexible disaster logistics may help to stabilize the situation more efficiently and stimulate affected people and communities to overcome the (threatening) situation. The integration of psycho-social support at an early stage is crucial.

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